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Abstract book

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Established and emerging biomarkers in cervical cancer prognosis and response to therapy

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Background: Cervical cancer remains a leading cause of global morbidity and mortality among women. The true cost of this disease cannot be measured by years of life lost alone; as many women are diagnosed in their prime child rearing and economically productive years, the impact of treatment and death are felt by many. Efforts to improve survival and reduce morbidity from cervical cancer include the identification of biomarkers to predict risk of recurrence and death.

Objective: To discuss the established biomarkers of cervical cancer response to therapy and survival, and to review emerging biomarkers that serve both predictive and prognostic roles.

Findings: The International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) 2018 Report on cervical cancer provides a prognostic stage grouping which incorporates the negative impact of lymph node metastases in addition to advanced primary tumor stage. Beyond FIGO stage, the use of 18F-FDG PET/CT has become a standard part of staging and response assessment in the 3-month post-treatment time point where this resource is available. Serum levels of tumor markers including squamous cell carcinoma antigen (SCCA) are used in some clinical settings to provide prognostic information and indicate early recurrence of disease. Emerging biomarkers may provide both predictive and prognostic information, and may also provide insight into the underlying biologic heterogeneity of cervical cancer. These include imaging-based biomarkers such as 18F-FDG PET metrics, functional MRI at diagnosis and during chemoradiation, and radiomics and radiogenomic analyses. HPV subtype, integration, and clearance rate may also represent targetable biomarkers for new therapeutic approaches. Circulating biomarkers such as SCCA have been found to play a molecular role within tumor cells actively protecting cells against radiation and chemotherapy, and may contribute to an immune microenvironment that benefits the tumor. Other non-invasive biomarkers such as circu-

lating tumor or HPV DNA are tools that may be more accessible to the world's largest populations of patients diagnosed with cervical cancer, and should be a priority for further development.

Conclusions: The rate of cervical cancer related mortality has not changed in decades despite implementation of advanced treatment techniques. Biomarkers for cervical cancer prognostication, predictive of response to current therapies and productive of new treatment approaches are urgently needed for cervical cancer.

Keywords: cervical cancer, biomarkers, prognosis

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